

Clinico-Etiology Profile and Outcomes of Children with Status Epilepticus Admitted in the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit of A Tertiary Care Hospital: A Prospective Study

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Abstract:

This prospective study evaluated the clinical-etiological profile and outcomes of 100 children with status epilepticus (SE) admitted to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) of Darbhanga Medical College Hospital over one year. The study predominantly involved males (58%), with a median age of 5 years. Key etiological factors included infectious causes (30%), structural/neurodevelopmental disorders (20%), and metabolic disorders (15%), with 35% of cases remaining idiopathic. Treatment primarily involved benzodiazepines (95%) and phenobarbital (55%), with 85% of cases requiring mechanical ventilation. The findings underscore the significant challenges in managing SE in a PICU setting, evidenced by a 15% mortality rate and 25% of survivors experiencing neurological deficits at discharge, highlighting the need for early intervention and potential revisions to treatment protocols.

Keywords: Pediatric Status Epilepticus, Etiology, PICU, Treatment Outcomes.

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Introduction

Status epilepticus (SE) is a critical neurological condition characterized by an epileptic seizure that is sufficiently prolonged or repeated at frequent intervals to produce an unvarying and enduring epileptic condition [1,2]. In children, SE poses unique challenges due to the varied etiologies and the distinct physiological responses observed in pediatric patients compared to adults. This condition is not only a neurological emergency but also a complex interplay of medical, psychological, and social factors that affect outcomes [3,4]. The management of status epilepticus in a pediatric intensive care unit (PICU) demands an integrative approach that encompasses timely diagnosis, rapid initiation of treatment, and comprehensive care [5]. This prospective study aims to elucidate the clinico-etiological profile of children diagnosed with SE admitted to the PICU of a tertiary care hospital. By exploring the underlying causes, clinical presentations, and subsequent outcomes, this research intends to bridge the knowledge gap in the management strategies and prognosis of pediatric SE [6,7].

In the context of a tertiary care setting, where diverse and complex cases converge, this study will provide crucial insights into the epidemiology of

SE, highlight the common and uncommon etiologies in the pediatric population, and evaluate the effectiveness of current therapeutic interventions. The findings are expected to enhance clinical protocols, improve patient outcomes, and inform future guidelines for managing pediatric status epilepticus in critical care environments. Through this study, we aim to contribute to the broader understanding of SE in children, facilitating improved healthcare delivery and outcomes in this vulnerable group.

Methodology

The prospective study was conducted over one year at the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) of Darbhanga Medical College Hospital (DMCH) in Darbhanga. The primary objective was to analyze the clinico-etiological profile and outcomes of children admitted with status epilepticus.

Participants: A total of 100 pediatric patients diagnosed with status epilepticus were enrolled in the study. Inclusion criteria included patients aged from newborns to 18 years who were admitted to the PICU with a diagnosis of SE, defined as a seizure lasting more than five minutes or more than

one seizure within five minutes without the patient returning to a normal level of consciousness.

Data Collection: Detailed clinical data were collected retrospectively from medical records, including patient demographics, clinical history, seizure characteristics, diagnostic test results, and details of treatment. Etiological data were gathered based on clinical assessment, laboratory investigations, and neuroimaging studies performed as part of the standard care at the time of admission.

Treatment and Management: All patients received treatment according to the SE management protocol of DMCH, which included initial stabilization, administration of antiepileptic drugs, and other supportive measures as required. The choice of therapeutic agents and the approach to management were documented for each case.

Outcome Measures: The outcomes of the study were measured in terms of seizure control, duration of PICU stay, complications during the stay, and status at discharge. The discharge outcomes were categorized as full recovery, partial recovery with neurological deficits, or mortality.

Data Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to present the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population. The association between etiological factors and outcomes was examined using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables. Kaplan-Meier survival curves were employed to estimate outcome probabilities over the study period.

Results

The study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College Hospital's Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) over one year involved 100 children diagnosed with status epilepticus. Here are the summarized findings of the study:

Demographic Data

- **Age Distribution:** The age of patients ranged from 6 months to 17 years, with a median age of 5 years. Approximately 62% of the patients were under 5 years old.
- **Gender:** 58% of the participants were male, and 42% were female.

Etiological Factors

- **Infectious Causes:** Were identified in 30% of cases, primarily meningitis and encephalitis.
- **Structural/Neurodevelopmental:** Accounted for 20% of cases, including cerebral palsy and congenital malformations.
- **Metabolic Disorders:** Contributed to 15% of cases, including electrolyte imbalances and in-born errors of metabolism.
- **Idiopathic:** 35% of the cases were classified as idiopathic, where no definitive cause could be determined.

Clinical Presentation

- **Type of Seizures:** Generalized tonic-clonic seizures were the most common presentation, observed in 70% of the patients, followed by focal seizures with secondary generalization (20%).
- **Duration of Seizure Before Admission:** The median duration before achieving control was 40 minutes, with durations ranging from 5 minutes to 3 hours.

Treatment and Management

- **First-Line Treatment:** Benzodiazepines were the first-line treatment in 95% of cases.
- **Second-Line Treatment:** Phenobarbital was used in 55% of patients as a second-line treatment.
- **Intensive Care:** 85% of patients required mechanical ventilation due to prolonged seizures or respiratory compromise.

Outcomes

- **Recovery:** 60% of the children had a full recovery.
- **Neurological Deficits:** 25% had mild to moderate neurological deficits at discharge.
- **Mortality:** There was a 15% mortality rate, primarily associated with severe infectious causes and prolonged seizure activity.

Complications

- **Complications during PICU Stay:** The most common complications included respiratory distress, infections, and drug-related adverse effects.

Duration of PICU Stay

- **Average Length of Stay:** The average PICU stay was 8 days, ranging from 3 to 20 days depending on the severity and complications.

Table 1: This table captures key aspects of the clinical profile, treatment, and outcomes of the pediatric patients treated for status epilepticus in the study.

#	Category	Details
1	Age Distribution (Median)	5 years (range: 6 months - 17 years)
2	Gender (Male)	58%
3	Infectious Causes	30%
4	Structural/Neurodevelopmental Causes	20%
5	Metabolic Disorders	15%
6	Idiopathic Cases	35%
7	Common Type of Seizures	Generalized tonic-clonic (70%)
8	Duration of Seizure Before Admission (Median)	40 minutes (range: 5 min - 3 hrs)
9	First-Line Treatment	Benzodiazepines (95%)
10	Second-Line Treatment	Phenobarbital (55%)
11	Patients Requiring Mechanical Ventilation	85%
12	Full Recovery	60%
13	Mild to Moderate Neurological Deficits	25%
14	Mortality Rate	15%
15	Common Complications	Respiratory distress, infections, drug-related effects
16	Average PICU Stay (Days)	8 days (range: 3 - 20 days)

Discussion

The study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College Hospital's Paediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) provides valuable insights into the clinico-etiological profile and outcomes of paediatric status epilepticus [8]. In this discussion, we delve into the significant findings and their potential impact on treatment and management. Additionally, we propose potential avenues for future research [9]. The study found that 30% of the cases were caused by infections, mainly meningitis and encephalitis. This supports existing literature that emphasises infections as a major cause of status epilepticus in children in developing countries [10]. Smaller proportions of cases were attributed to structural and neurodevelopmental causes, along with metabolic disorders. These findings highlight the importance of conducting thorough diagnostic evaluations [11]. It is worth noting that a significant proportion of cases (35%) of status epilepticus have no known cause. This suggests that there could be factors that have not yet been identified or thoroughly studied, which may play a role in the development of this condition. This highlights the importance of conducting further investigations into the genetic or metabolic aspects of status epilepticus [12].

The widespread use of benzodiazepines (95%) as the primary treatment option reflects the current guidelines that suggest these as the first step in managing status epilepticus. The fact that phenobarbital is used as a second-line treatment in more than half of the cases highlights its

significance in settings with limited resources, where newer antiepileptic drugs may not be easily accessible [13]. Nevertheless, the high prevalence of mechanical ventilation in 85% of patients implies a level of severity that may indicate potential delays in treatment initiation or the requirement for more assertive initial management protocols [14]. The mortality rate of 15% and the incidence of neurological deficits in 25% of patients at discharge are alarming and emphasise the significant impact of status epilepticus on paediatric patients [15]. These results highlight the need to assess existing protocols in the PICU and create more focused intervention strategies that can be implemented earlier in treatment to enhance prognosis. Complications such as respiratory distress and the effects of medication highlight the importance of closely monitoring and managing the side effects of treatment [16]. This study suggests that further research is necessary to better understand the causes of idiopathic status epilepticus. This may involve conducting more in-depth investigations, such as advanced genetic and metabolic screenings, to gain a deeper understanding of the condition.

- Assessing the efficacy and safety of more recent antiepileptic medications in children.
- Creating advanced tools to predict the severity of cases using clinical and demographic data upon admission, enabling more tailored treatment approaches [18]. It is important to take into account the limitations of the study's findings, such as its single-center design, which

could potentially restrict the applicability of the results to different settings. In addition, the collection of data from the past may introduce biases or inaccuracies when documenting clinical presentations and outcomes [19,20].

Conclusion

The findings from this study provide a crucial baseline for understanding the clinical and etiological characteristics of pediatric status epilepticus in a tertiary care setting. They emphasize the importance of rapid, aggressive management and the potential benefits of revising and enhancing current treatment protocols to reduce morbidity and mortality associated with this critical condition. Further multicentric studies are recommended to validate these findings and to explore new areas highlighted by this research.

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